

An Integrated Life-Course Approach for Person-Centred Solutions and Care for Ageing with Multi-morbidity in the European Regions – STAGE; Stay Healthy Through Ageing

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GIS	Geographic information systems
NCDs	Non-communicable diseases
NHAI	Neighbourhood healthy ageing index
WP	Work Package

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INTRODUCTION

Rationale

The proportion of older adults in Europe is increasing rapidly, posing significant public health challenges [1]. A key concern is the rising prevalence of chronic age-related diseases, including cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, and cancer [2,3]. These chronic conditions require continuous management and extensive healthcare services, placing a substantial burden on individuals and healthcare systems. Furthermore, health conditions increasingly co-occur in individuals [4], driving up co-morbidity rates of older adults, resulting in increased societal costs and reduced quality of life and well-being [5-7].

Addressing the challenges of population ageing necessitates a comprehensive approach that includes effective management strategies, but above all, preventive strategies to reduce or delay the onset of diseases in later life [8]. To develop such strategies, it is crucial to understand the underlying factors influencing health and disease in this demographic.

It has been demonstrated that the broader environments in which people live can influence the development of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) [9-11]. Consequently, these environments represent an important potential target for preventive strategies. Characteristics of the neighbourhood environment can exert an indirect impact on health over time, influencing lifestyle behavioural habits such as physical inactivity, sedentary behaviours and unhealthy dietary behaviours. For instance, through low walkability of neighbourhoods, unhealthy food environments, and low social cohesion/support. Other indirect influences on health include the effect of noise pollution on sleep quality and psychological well-being [12, 13]. Moreover, environments can directly impact NCDs through physico-chemical exposures, such as air pollution [14].

Although NCDs and multimorbidity are becoming increasingly prevalent in younger age groups, the neighbourhood environments in which people live in later life may have a significant impact on the progression and management of these diseases, while also minimizing the risk of developing multimorbidity in individuals already suffering from one or more chronic conditions.

Exposure to environmental factors rarely occurs in isolation. Rather, people are simultaneously exposed to a variety of factors. Interactions between these factors collectively influence health outcomes [15]. This highlights the complexity of real-world scenarios. To address this complexity, gaining better insights in the relation between combined exposures on health and so develop effective preventive strategies, it is essential to examine environmental factors collectively rather than in single-exposure studies as has been done often in the scientific field. Whereas single-exposure studies are useful to identify (domains of) exposures that may be especially relevant in healthy ageing; by embracing the interconnectedness of exposures, we can better understand their combined effects on health in older adults.

There is a growing body of research examining associations between environmental exposures and non-communicable diseases (NCDs), using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to objectively operationalise environmental factors. Based on the existing

knowledge, potentially important environmental factors have been identified. However, a comprehensive overview of the existing literature is still lacking, particularly for older populations. To address this gap, a systematic review of the associations between built environmental exposures (e.g. walkability, green space, food environment, land-use) with NCDs and multi-morbidity in community-dwelling older adults, is conducted (Task 3.1). The findings of this review provide insights into key environmental factors and the magnitude of their effects on chronic disease outcomes.

Identifying (the combination of) key environmental characteristics related to health and active ageing will provide entry points for quantifying these using GIS. Combining geographic exposures into an index has been done before and was proven useful. For instance, to characterise the walkability or drivability of environments. Combining and mapping exposures (potentially) related to (un)healthy ageing in an index will then enable heatmapping, benchmarking and monitoring problematic areas, and facilitate the implementation of upstream preventive approaches. To develop an actionable tool for researchers, policymakers, health professionals and the public at large, STAGE's WP3 is working towards an interactive EU-wide web-atlas that visualizes and quantifies the neighbourhood ageing (un)healthiness. The stepwise manner in which this atlas is developed is as follows:

1. Evidence synthesis by systematically reviewing and describing the published scientific literature on (1) built environmental exposures in their relation to ageing with NCDs and multi-morbidity, and on (2) senior-centred participatory approaches (Task 3.1);
2. Gathering input from experts in the form of an interactive workshop on the key environmental determinants of (un)healthy ageing.
3. Listing candidate exposures in an initial index (Task 3.2);
4. Gathering input from the target population through evidence-based participatory approaches (Task 3.3);
5. Collection and preparation of Europe-wide GIS data on selected exposures;
6. Translating findings into a Europe-wide atlas (Task 3.4).

This current Deliverable reports on Step 2 and 3. At this stage, we have developed one overall prototype with potentially relevant components rather than two different prototype versions. This is due to two reasons: 1) The input of target population will likely change the selection and nature of some components. This input will be gathered in the next phase; and 2) the index for selected local areas will be further informed after the final selection of focus areas is made (expected Q2, 2026).

INDEX DEVELOPMENT

Process summary

The initial development phase yielded a comprehensive longlist of exposures that are potentially associated with multi-morbidity and NCDs in older adults. The longlist represents a preliminary effort to consolidate diverse factors influencing health. Environmental exposures are included based on the evidence synthesized in Task 3.1 of WP3 (i.e. to meta-review the scientific evidence on built environment-related exposome factors in their relation to ageing with multi-morbidity; and on senior-centred participatory approaches), as well as theory guided by theoretical frameworks, and expert input. In addition, a workshop with the full STAGE consortium was held during the STAGE General Assembly in Amsterdam on 10 of September 2024. During the workshop, a preliminary list of environmental exposures was ranked by importance by all individual consortium members attending the assembly (n=68). Additional input from members on potentially significant exposures was also collected and documented.

Longlist of Environmental Exposures

Table 1 presents the initial Neighbourhood Healthy Ageing Index (NHAI) in the form of a longlist of exposures and composite measures, structured by five domains: (1) the built environment, (2) the physico-chemical environment, (3) the food environment, (4) the social environment, and (5) other. Each domain contains a list of exposures, theoretically and empirically suggested to be associated with NCDs and multimorbidity in older adults. Furthermore, a number of objective measurement methods that are commonly employed for the assessment of environmental exposures were documented. It should be noted that this list is not exhaustive and that there may be instances where domains and exposures overlap.

Table 1. Longlist of environmental exposures of the initial Neighbourhood Healthy Ageing Index (NHA)

Domain	Exposure	Measurement	Comments
Built environment	Land use mix	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entropy index 	<i>Classes may include residential, commercial, recreational, industrial, agricultural, etc.</i>
	Residential density	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Population density 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Housing unit density 	
	Presence and accessibility of destinations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proximity to/ number of/ diversity of destinations 	<i>Destinations may include retail facilities, sports facilities, recreational facilities, community centres, parks, pharmacies, etc.</i>
	Presence and accessibility of public transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of public transport stops 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity of public transport modes 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Affordability of public transport 	
	Street connectivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Density of intersections 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Street network complexity 	
	Pedestrian friendly features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of street furniture (e.g. benches) 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sidewalk coverage/ width/ condition 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slope/ altitude 		<i>The condition of the sidewalk could be measured in terms of its evenness, variations in altitude, the presence of</i>	

			<i>obstacles, and accessibility features like curb ramps.</i>	
	Green spaces	• Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)		
		• Percentage of green space		
	Blue spaces	• Proximity to nearest blue space (i.e. water)		
		• Visibility Index		
	Walkability	• Walkability index		<i>* Composite measure containing a selection of above-listed components</i>
	Driveability	• Distance to highway exists and entries, parking pressure, paid parking		<i>* Composite measure</i>
Bike-ability	• Bike path density, amenities, safety from motorised traffic	<i>* Composite measure</i>		
Physico-chemical environment	Noise pollution	• Proximity to major roadways/ airports/ trams		
		• Sound level measures (dB or dBA)		
	Air pollution	• Levels of PM10 and PM2.5		
		• Nitrogen dioxide		
	Heat levels	• Urban heat islands		
		• Infrared Thermography		
	Pesticide exposure	• Distance of residence to agricultural sites where pesticides are used		

Food environment	Availability of (un)healthy foods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence, proximity and healthfulness of food outlets 	
Social environment	Crime rates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequency of criminal incidents 	
	Social cohesion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of community centres/ public spaces 	<i>Public spaces may include (city)parks, community gardens, libraries, etc.</i>
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Volunteering rates 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of single households 	
	Social support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TBD 	
	Neighbourhoods socio-economic position	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational attainment 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Income level 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neighbourhood deprivation index (NDI) 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Home ownership rates 	
	Demographic diversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethnic/ racial diversity (diversity index) 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Income equality 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age distribution 			
Residential stability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Length of residence 		
Income inequality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gini coefficient 		
Food insecurity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage of neighbourhood residents experiencing food insecurity 		
Other	Traffic safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relative incidence of accidents 	

	Aesthetics	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Litter, graffiti, architecture, building quality, etc.	<i>Inherently subjective but may include proxy indicators such as proximity to parks/green/ blue spaces, littering, vandalism, or decay.</i>
	Arts and culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Presence of (industrial) heritage landmarks or sites• Presence and access to arts and cultural amenities and activities	

CONCLUSION

The initial phase of index development has been successfully completed, resulting in the creation of a comprehensive longlist of environmental exposures. Moving forward, the prioritization of exposures, coupled with validation and stakeholder engagement as will be done in Task 3.3, will provide a selected list for which high-resolution GIS measures are obtained in a standardised way for the whole of Europe. For many of these exposures there are GIS measures mapped already, in the context of STAGE, but also in other EC-funded projects (particularly OBCT and EXPANSE). Furthermore, a more comprehensive index for regional areas will be developed where analyses are foreseen in the context of WP4. A first identified region is the Turin region (Italy). A region-specific index allows for inclusion of locally available data that may not be available for the whole of Europe (especially related to social-environmental exposures), and can result in a more refined and holistic index.

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